

La Jolla beach amagmatic geothermal system, Baja California, Mexico: controls on the thermal anomaly from 3D thermal–hydraulic simulations

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ABSTRACT

Amagmatic geothermal systems that discharge in coastal areas are promising renewable energy resources for seawater desalination and electricity production. These systems arise from the deep circulation of meteoric water and seawater along regional fault zones in uplifted orogenic belts. They are characterized by diffuse hot water discharge (<100 °C) in the intertidal zone at low tide. In order to assess their energy potential, more fundamental insights are needed to understand the coupled thermal–hydraulic–chemical–mechanical processes controlling their behavior. In this contribution, we present large-scale 3D thermal–hydraulic numerical simulations of the amagmatic geothermal system at La Jolla beach (Pacific coast), which is linked to the steeply dipping dextral Agua Blanca Fault (ABF) that traverses northern Baja California, Mexico. With a temperature of up to 94 °C, the discharge of hot water at La Jolla beach represents the inland hottest manifestation of amagmatic geothermal systems worldwide. Simulations were run for a large 3D domain of 20 × 10 × 14 km using the software Toughreact. The aims were to (i) assess the role of surface topography and nearshore seafloor bathymetry in controlling regional water circulation through the ABF and (ii) obtain a fundamental understanding of the processes causing the very high discharge temperatures at La Jolla beach. All simulations were run by specifying hydrostatic pressure and conductive temperature distributions as initial and boundary conditions. The simulations were constrained by field observations such as discharge temperatures (up to 94 °C), the extent of the La Jolla beach thermal anomaly (~300 × 100 m), water residence times (15 ka), and seawater mixing fraction (20%). Different fault widths and permeability configurations were tested. Modeling results indicate that fluid flow within the ABF is controlled by the surface topography and, more importantly, by the hydrostatic pressure defined by the Pacific Ocean and its salinity. These boundary conditions lead to fluid upflow beneath La Jolla beach, which occurs independently of the permeability and width of the ABF. However, assuming a homogeneous permeability along the ABF (100 m wide zone with $k = 1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$) produces an extreme and unrealistically shallow geothermal anomaly of ~0.35 km width × 3.3 km length with temperatures below 100 °C. However, the field observations can be reproduced by inserting a vertical 100 × 100 m zone with high permeability ($k = 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$) into the model below La Jolla beach along the ABF ($k = 8.0 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2$). This preferential upflow zone controls the shape and magnitude of the resulting shallow thermal anomaly. Our observations suggest that the highest fluxes and temperatures in amagmatic, orogenic geothermal systems occur where strong hydraulic head gradients, such as the coastline or below major valley floors, coincide with highly permeable pathways along regional faults. Therefore, geothermal exploration for amagmatic geothermal systems should focus on permeable faults that cross areas with high hydraulic head gradients.

1. Introduction

La Jolla beach is a coastal amagmatic geothermal system hosted by the Agua Blanca Fault (ABF) located northwest of the Punta Banda Peninsula in Baja California, Mexico (Fig. 1). Evidence of this system is the thermal water that emanates diffusely from the intertidal zone and is visible only at low tide. Using Thermal InfraRed images acquired by drone, Carbajal-Martínez et al. (2020) showed that the surface temperature at La Jolla beach is up to 52 °C, while at 20 cm below the surface, the temperature is up to 94 °C. In addition, they estimated that the footprint of the thermal anomaly is $\sim 300 \times 100$ m. Owing to its location and high temperature, this hydrothermal system is considered a valuable geothermal resource that could supply the energy demand of a multi-effect distillation plant (MED) to desalinate seawater and cover the shortage of fresh water in the region. The desalination costs of a MED are comparable to those of a reverse osmosis plant powered by fossil fuels. (0.8 US\$ m⁻³; Wendt, 2017).

To take full advantage of this geothermal resource, it is necessary to understand the fundamental processes controlling its behavior. In this contribution, we present large-scale 3D thermal-hydraulic numerical simulations of the amagmatic geothermal system at La Jolla beach to (i) assess the role of surface topography and nearshore seafloor bathymetry in controlling regional water circulation through the ABF, and (ii) obtain a fundamental understanding of the processes causing the very high discharge temperatures. Our simulations are constrained by field observations such as surface location and temperature, size of the thermal anomaly, and seawater mixing fractions.

1.1 Structural and geothermal features of the study area

Punta Banda Peninsula has an optimal structural setting for the formation of amagmatic geothermal systems due to the lack of magmatic activity since the Miocene and to the high degree of extension of normal faults in the center of the Peninsula (orientation $\sim N37^\circ W$ and dips from 45° to $70^\circ SW$; Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez and Suárez-Vidal, 1988). Owing to the active dextral branches of the ABF on each side of the Punta Banda Peninsula (Fig. 1), this area shows the greatest extension along the entire length (~ 150 km) of the ABF trace (Wetmore et al., 2019). Uplift rates are also high, with 12 marine terraces having been uplifted over the past 1.3 Ma (Fig. 1B; Rockwell et al., 1989). These terraces geographically coincide with amagmatic geothermal systems as evidenced by the discharge of thermal waters at three distinct locations across the Punta Banda Peninsula (Fig. 1B). These locations are El Retiro beach with a discharge temperature of 35 °C, a fumarolic submarine field on the southeastern side of the Peninsula (102 °C), and La Jolla beach (94 °C; Vidal et al., 1981; Carbajal-Martínez, 2019; Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2020).

Fig. 1. A) Location of the study area. B) Structural setting and location of amagmatic geothermal systems of the Punta Banda Peninsula, Baja California, Mexico.

La Jolla Beach is the focus of our study. It is worth mentioning that 500 m around the coastal anomaly, there are shallow domestic wells that record temperatures between 29 and 73 °C (Fig. 2). Additionally, Arango-Galván et al. (2011) and Carbajal-Martínez, (2019) reported the distribution of rock resistivity in four electrical resistivity tomography sections (up to 80 m depth, Fig. 2). These sections reveal the presence of a conductive anomaly ($0.8 \Omega \text{ m}$) beneath the coastal thermal anomaly of La Jolla, implying the presence of thermal and saline waters in the subsurface.

The chemical composition of the thermal waters discharging at La Jolla Beach, including their dissolved gas concentrations, is described in detail by Carbajal-Martínez et al. (2023). In short, the thermal waters are characterized by a slightly acidic pH (5 to 7) and a lower salinity (8.5 to 16 g L^{-1}) than local seawater (8.0 and 34.0 g L^{-1} , respectively). The isotopic values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ reveal that thermal water originates from rainwater recharged in the mountainous zone and mixed with seawater in the coastal zone. In addition, the ^3He fraction within the dissolved He is less than 3%, implying that the contribution of He from the mantle is negligible and confirms the amagmatic nature of the hydrothermal system.

The design of our numerical simulations is based on the following conceptual model of geothermal activity in the study area (Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2023). Meteoric water recharges in the inland mountains (Fig. 1B) and is driven by topographically controlled head gradients through the crystalline basement and may reach down to the brittle–ductile transition zone (12 km), the lower limit for advective fluid flow. The temperature of the meteoric water increases during infiltration according to the average geothermal gradient of $24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C km}^{-1}$. Beneath La Jolla beach, the heated water quickly ascends towards the surface through a highly permeable section of the ABF and finally discharges as a thermal spring. Along its flow path, the infiltrated meteoric water mixes with seawater-like ancient porewater, and near the coast, with fresh seawater.

Fig. 2. A) Temperature and size of the La Jolla Beach thermal anomaly (Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2020) as well the location of six surrounding domestic wells (yellow markers) and four electrical resistivity tomography profiles (black lines P1 to P4). B) Electrical resistivity tomography sections for the four profiles shown in A (Carbajal-Martínez, 2019). The vertical black lines in sections P3 and P4 illustrate the location and depth of domestic wells.

2. Numerical simulator

Our forward coupled thermal-hydraulic numerical simulations were performed using the integral finite difference code TOUGHREACT V3 (Xu et al., 2014). All simulations were performed using the equation of state EOS1, allowing the simulation of pure water in its liquid, vapor, and two-phase states (Pruess et al., 1999). The temperature dependence of pure water properties such as viscosity, specific density, and enthalpy are calculated from steam table equations (International Formulation Committee, 1967). EOS1 simulates water and coupled heat flow according to the mass balance equation:

$$\frac{\partial M_{W,H}}{\partial t} = -\nabla F_{W,H} + q_{W,H} \quad (1)$$

where $M_{W,H}$ is the accumulation term for water M_W (kg m^{-3}) or heat M_H (J m^{-3}), $F_{W,H}$ is the water flux F_W ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) or heat flux F_H ($\text{J m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), and $q_{W,H}$ are water or heat sinks (−) or sources (+). For fully saturated, single-phase flow problems F_W is equal to the Darcy flux u (m s^{-1})

$$u = -\frac{k}{\mu} (\nabla P - \rho g) \quad (2)$$

where k is the intrinsic permeability (m^2) of the rock, μ is the water viscosity (Pa s), ∇P (Pa m^{-1}) is the hydraulic head gradient, ρ is the density of water (kg m^{-3}), and g is the acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2}). Heat flux F_H ($\text{J m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is defined as

$$F_H = C_M \times T \times \rho_M \times u - \lambda \times \nabla T \quad (3)$$

where C_M ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and ρ_M (kg m^{-3}) are the specific heat capacity and the density of the porous medium, T (K) is the temperature of the porous medium, λ is the thermal conductivity of the wet rock ($\text{J s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), and the gradient in temperature between adjacent grid blocks is ∇T (K m^{-1}).

2.1 Model geometry

Our numerical model covers a large 3D domain of $20 \times 10 \times 14$ km. The model is discretized using an initially regular rectangular mesh consisting of ca. 200,000 grid blocks. The size of the grid blocks is variable, whereas the highest resolution is in the La Jolla beach area ($25 \times 25 \times 10$ m). The variability of block size in the X and Y directions is shown in Figure 3.

Our 3D model domain explicitly considers the topography (max. 1 km) and bathymetry (max. 0.5 km) of the study area (Fig. 3A). In order to incorporate the morphology of the area, a digital elevation model (DEM) was downloaded from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA National Geophysical Data Center, 2006). Subsequently, the DEM was used to numerically shape the surface of the initial regular mesh using the "fit surface" PyTOUGH method (Croucher, 2015). This resulted in an irregular mesh explicitly considering the topography of the Punta Banda Peninsula and the seafloor bathymetry (Fig. 3B).

Fig. 3. A) Topographic and bathymetric map of the model domain. B) Mesh configuration for all simulations along with the topography and bathymetry values. C) Model setup showing four domains in 3D view: Agua Blanca Fault, host rock, a preferential upflow zone beneath La Jolla beach, and the brittle–ductile transition zone, which defines the base of the model.

2.2 Initial and boundary conditions

All simulations were performed by specifying the initial conditions of hydrostatic pressure and conductive temperature distributions. A fixed temperature was set at the upper boundary assuming an ambient temperature of 16 °C at the coast (CICESE, 2019), an adiabatic cooling rate of $-5.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C km}^{-1}$ over the continent, and a cooling gradient of $-3.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C per 100 m depth}$ in the seawater column (h) (Emery and Dewar, 1982).

Over the continent, the atmospheric pressure varies according to the altitude (z ; Cavcar, 2000). Consequently, we used the following equation to define the pressure at the upper model boundary, which was fixed throughout the simulations

$$P_{continent} = 10^5 \times [1 - (0.0065 \times z / 289.15)]^{5.2561} \quad (6)$$

Over the Pacific Ocean, the seafloor was defined as an upper model boundary. The pressure on this boundary was fixed by the seawater column length (h), density ($\rho_{seawater} = 1025 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), and g , the acceleration due to gravity (m s^{-2})

$$P_{seafloor} = \rho_{seawater} \times g \times h \quad (7)$$

Assuming an initial conductive temperature distribution, the temperature increases with depth according to the regional geothermal gradient of $24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C km}^{-1}$ (Carbajal-Martínez, 2019). At the lower model boundary (13 km below sea level), the temperature was fixed at $335 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, according to the geothermal gradient, the mean altitude of the surface topography (0.23 km), and the mean annual temperature at sea level ($16 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Three lateral and lower model boundaries were open for conductive heat exchange and closed for fluid flow. The upper model boundary and the lateral boundary in the direction of the Pacific Ocean were open for both heat and fluid flow.

2.3 Model parameters

In the study area, there are no hydraulic well test measurements that could be used to define the permeability within the model domain. Therefore, we have kept the model as simple as possible. The model was divided into four domains (Fig. 3C): host rock, fault zone, preferential upflow zone, and brittle–ductile transition. We assume a homogeneous permeability distribution for the host rock (granite) and fault zone, and we ignored any depth dependence of the permeability and porosity. Host rock and fault permeability values were taken from other studies in a similar geologic and tectonic setting (Table 1; Alt-Epping et al., 2021; Wanner et al., 2019).

For the host rock, we use a permeability of 10^{-18} m^2 and a porosity of 1% for all numerical simulations. Fault permeability ranges from 8×10^{-15} to $1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ according to different fault widths (25, 50, 75, 100 m), and porosity is 2%. For the brittle–ductile transition (model base), we use a low permeability (10^{-25} m^2) and a porosity of 1%. On the other hand, additional simulations were performed using a 1D preferential upflow zone with a footprint of $100 \times 100 \text{ m}$ beneath La Jolla beach. Permeability values for the preferential upflow zone are varied from 10^{-14} to 10^{-13} m^2 with a porosity fixed at 4%. We use a homogeneous distribution of the bulk rock density, thermal conductivity, and specific heat capacity in the four domains (Table 1).

Table 1
Material properties

Parameter	Fault	Preferential upflow zone	Host rock	BDT ^a
Permeability (m^2)	8×10^{-15} – 1.5×10^{-14}	10^{-14} – 10^{-13}	10^{-18}	10^{-25}
Porosity	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01
Bulk rock density (kg m^{-3})	2660	2660	2660	2660
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	3.35	3.35	3.35	3.35
Specific heat capacity ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	920	920	920	920

^a Brittle–ductile transition

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Location of the upflow zone

The results of the 3D thermal–hydraulic simulations without any preferential upflow zone are shown for a northwest-southeast (NW-SE) profile along the ABF (Fig. 4A). The temperature distribution and flow vectors demonstrate that there is a water upflow zone in the coastal area due to the infiltration of meteoric water as well as seawater into the crystalline basement along the ABF (Fig. 4B). Darcy flux profiles illustrate that the upflow zone is always located in the coastal zone independently of the fault width and fault permeability (Fig 4C). The upflow zone spatially correlates with the lowest hydrostatic pressure (highest hydraulic head gradient) along the entire ABF (Fig. 4D), demonstrating that the regional-scale hydraulic regime causes the thermal anomaly at La Jolla beach. The precise location of the discharge zone is controlled by the balance of hydrostatic pressures between (i) the seawater column of the Pacific Ocean and (ii) the meteoric water column of the mountainous onshore zone. This is illustrated in detail in Figure 4E, showing the result of three simulations with a different implementation of the fixed pressure (eq. 7) at the seawater model boundary: (i) no seawater present (i.e., $P_{fixed} = 1$ bar), (ii) seawater with a density of pure water ($\rho_{seawater}$: 997 kg m^{-3}), (iii) seawater with a correct density of 1025 kg m^{-3} . The thermal anomaly and thus the upflow zone occur below La Jolla beach only when the correct seawater density is used to specify the seawater model boundary (simulation (iii)). In simulations (i) and (ii), in contrast, the upflow zone occurs 11 and 2 km offshore from the coastline. The results shown in Figure 4C thus demonstrate that the hydrostatic pressure of the Pacific Ocean plays a key role in controlling the location of the thermal anomaly, while the permeability of the fault controls the discharge temperature of thermal waters. It should be noted, however, that the resulting water upflow (Fig. 4B) generates a rather large coastal geothermal anomaly with a length of ~ 4 km along the ABF when the fault width and permeability are calibrated to 100 m and $k = 1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ in order to match the $94 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ surface temperature observed at La Jolla Beach. Although we have little information on the extent of the subsurface anomaly, the one obtained from the calibrated simulation appears to be unrealistically large, implying that not all relevant processes are captured by the model.

Fig. 4. Results of numerical thermal–hydraulic simulations using a homogeneous permeability along the ABF, shown in profiles along the NW–SE strike of the fault. Plotted values of Darcy flow, hydrostatic pressure, and temperature correspond to a depth of 15 m below the surface and seafloor. A) Topographic and bathymetric profile. B) Temperature (°C) and flow velocity vectors (m s⁻¹) show that the length of the near-surface thermal anomaly is extreme (~ 4 km) for a fault width of 100 m and fault permeability of $1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$. C) Water flow velocity vector of the z component (m s⁻¹) along the ABF showing that the maximum flux occurs in the coastal zone independently of the chosen fault width and permeability. D) Hydrostatic pressure (MPa) along the ABF shows that the lowest hydrostatic pressure is located in the coastal zone. E) Temperature distribution (°C) of three simulations involving a 100 m wide fault and a permeability of $1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ but with different implementations of the seawater boundary.

3.2 Effects of preferential upflow zones

Previous studies agree that along regional faults there are preferential pathways for fluid circulation, in which permeability is enhanced by complex structural features such as dilational jogs, linkage and intersection zones between fault segments, and highly fractured damage zones. (e.g., Caine et al., 1996; Faulkner et al., 2010). In the study area, the structural setting is complex (see Section 1.1), and field evidence (marine terraces and normal fault displacements) indicate that near La Jolla beach there may be enhanced permeability due to the large extensional component of the ABF. For this reason, and because of the large size of the thermal anomaly that results from simulations assuming a homogeneous fault zone permeability (Fig. 4B), we decided to perform additional numerical simulations incorporating a vertical 1D pathway representing a preferential upflow with a footprint of 100×100 m. Table 1 shows the results of testing different permeability values for this pathway.

Simulations involving a fault zone 100 m wide ($k = 8.0 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2$) and a preferential upflow zone with 4% porosity result in heated water reaching the surface at $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as soon as the permeability of the preferential pathway is greater than $6 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ (Fig. 5A). Once the permeability of the preferential pathway is increased to 10^{-13} m^2 , the temperature reaches $\sim 90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and thus matches the observed temperature at La Jolla beach. Under steady state conditions, which are reached after about 15 kyr (Fig. 5B), this simulation yields seawater and rainwater fractions of $\sim 20\%$ and 80% , respectively (Fig. 5C). These fractions agree well with those reported by Carbajal-Martínez et al. (2023), demonstrating that the geothermal system is dominated by infiltration of rainwater in the mountainous hinterland, driven by the high, topographically induced hydraulic head gradients.

Implementing the permeable upflow zone in our simulations considerably decreases the length of the thermal anomaly at La Jolla beach for the calibrated models that match the $94 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ discharge temperature (Fig. 6A). When the fault zone is assigned a homogeneous permeability, the anomaly is 3.3 km long (Fig. 6B). In contrast, when a preferential upflow path is inserted beneath La Jolla beach, the anomaly is only 475 m long (Fig. 6C). Assuming that the ~ 500 m length over which domestic wells are distributed near La Jolla beach approximately captures the true extent of the thermal anomaly (Fig. 1), the simulation incorporating a 1D permeable upflow path seems quite realistic. By implementing this preferential pathway, we are thus able to reproduce all manifestations of the thermal anomaly, including its discharge temperature, size, location, and seawater mixing fraction.

Fig. 5. Temperature and tracer fraction (meteoric water and seawater) at 15 m below La Jolla beach obtained by incorporating a preferential upflow zone in the simulation. A) Temperature as a function of assumed permeability (k) of the preferential upflow zone. B) Temperature vs. time, demonstrating that the simulation reaches a steady state after approximately 15 kyr. C) Tracer fraction of seawater and meteoric water as a function of time. Values shown in B and C correspond to a 100 m wide fault with a permeability of $8.0 \times 10^{-15} m^2$ and permeability of the preferential upflow zone of $10^{-13} m^2$.

Fig. 6. A) Depth section along the ABF showing temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and fluid velocity vectors (m s^{-1}) resulting from a simulation that includes a preferential upflow path beneath La Jolla beach. Yellow dashed line shows the much longer thermal anomaly (100°C isotherm) that results if the preferential upflow path is omitted from the model. B) Plan view of the thermal anomaly at 30 m depth ($T \geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$) resulting from simulations in which the ABF has a homogeneous permeability. C) Same as panel B but with the inclusion of a preferential upflow path within the fault plane.

6. Conclusion

Thermal–hydraulic simulations carried out for the La Jolla beach system in Baja California, Mexico, demonstrate that the location and temperature of amagmatic coastal geothermal systems are controlled by the balance of hydrostatic pressure forces from the Ocean and adjacent onshore areas, as well as the permeability of major fault zones where advective subsurface fluid flow

occurs. Upflow zones of thermal waters are always located in the coastal zone because this is where the hydraulic pressure is minimized and where the upflow of heated water is facilitated. For the investigated case study at La Jolla beach, however, the additional definition of a highly permeable pathway beneath the discharge location was required to accurately match all manifestations of the thermal anomaly at the surface (discharge temperature, size, and location of the thermal anomaly, and seawater mixing fraction). Our study thus suggests that the most effective amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems occur where strong hydraulic head gradients below major valley floors or at the coastline coincide with highly permeable preferentially pathways along regional faults.

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